

ASPECTUAL COMPOSITION OF GRAMMATICAL CATEGORIES

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Annotation: The article is about grammatical categories and their types according to different features. As we know, grammatical category is a closed system of mutually exclusive and opposed to each other grammatical meanings (grammemes), which defines the division of a vast set of word forms (or a small set of high-frequency word forms with an abstract type of meaning) into non-intersecting classes, the difference between which significantly affects the degree of grammatical correctness of the text.

Key words: grammatical category, syntax, nominative, subjective-objective, relational, communicative, evaluative.

Grammatical category is a closed system of mutually exclusive and opposed to each other grammatical meanings (grammemes), which defines the division of a vast set of word forms (or a small set of high-frequency word forms with an abstract type of meaning) into non-intersecting classes, the difference between which significantly affects the degree of grammatical correctness of the text.

The property of mutual exclusion consists in the fact that any grammatical category is a set of grammatical meanings (grammars), which cannot be simultaneously expressed in one word-form (but one word-form can have grammars of several grammatical categories).

Thus, the category of number in Russian includes mutually exclusive

grammemes "singular" and "plural": they cannot be combined in one word-form. The grammeme "creative case" does not belong to the same category, as it can be freely expressed together with any of its grammemes.

Characteristic features of grammatical categories include:

- the modifying type of the categorising feature,
- its involvement in syntax,
- obligatory choice of one of its values for (word)forms from the categorised totality,
- the presence of a regular way of its expression.

The presence of the totality of these properties is usually the basis for the unconditional recognition of the grammatical character of a category, although each of them separately is neither a necessary nor a sufficient sign of a grammatical category.

According to the nature of grammatical meanings are distinguished:

- substantive (nominative, semantic, referential) grammatical categories directly involved in the reflection of extra-linguistic reality;
- formal (asemantic, formal-structural) categories, reflecting only purely combinatory limitations of word forms (e.g., concordant grammatical categories participate in the formation of agreement relations: for example, gender, number and case of an adjective, gender, number and person of a verb, as well as formal-structural morphological characteristics of lexemes, such as types of declension and conjugation).

Among the substantive grammatical categories are distinguished:

- nominative (objective, nominative, dictative; e.g., noun number, gender of animate nouns, animate nouns, degrees of comparison of an adjective, partly verb form, partly transitivity/non-transitivity and person/non-personality of a verb, concreteness/universality of reference);
- subjective-objective, reflecting the properties and relations of objects from

the point of view of the participants of the speech act;

- relational (syntactic) (noun case, adjective attributivity/predicativity, verb representation, communicative role).

Subjective-objective grammatical categories are subdivided into:

- Actualisation (deictic, shifter, indexical) (e.g. verb tense, person of pronouns);

- modal (e.g., verb inflection; referentiality/non-referentiality of a syntagma);

- communicative (e.g. definiteness/indefiniteness and communicative role of a syntagma);

- evaluative, i.e. expressing evaluation (e.g. degrees of intensity of a feature in predicate words, subjective evaluation in nouns);

- interpretative, reflecting the subjective point of view of the observer (verb voice, partly verb form, partly noun number, partly gender of animate nouns, partly animate nouns).

Relational grammatical categories are subdivided into:

- active (expressing valence, i.e. the ability to enter into syntactic relations with neighbouring words, e.g. transitivity/non-transitivity, person/non-personality, partly pledge and diathesis);

- passive (expressing the syntactic role of a word in an utterance, e.g. case of a noun, predicativity/attributivity of an adjective, representation of a verb).

- According to the relation of the categorical feature to the members of the partition, grammatical categories are subdivided into:

- formative (grammatical categories proper, correlative, modificatory), by which a lexeme can change (e.g. case of a noun; gender, number and case of an adjective; tense and inclination of a verb);

- classificatory (classificatory, non-correlative), peculiar to the whole lexeme and constant for it (e.g., parts of speech, gender of inanimate nouns, animate/inanimate nature of most nouns, transitivity/non-transitivity and

person/personality of most verbs).

According to the degree of "correlativity" among formative grammatical categories are distinguished:

- word-formation (consistently correlative, inflectional), modifying (i.e. assuming the presence of correlations) for all words of a given part of speech (case and number of a noun, tense and inclination of a verb, consonantal grammatical categories of verbs and adjectives);
- derivational (inconsistently correlative, base-formative, lexico-grammatical), implying correlations only for some significant subclass of a given part of speech (e.g., gender of animate nouns, kind and voice of verbs, degree of comparison of adjectives, diathesis).

Syntactic grammatical categories are divided into syntagmatic categories and paradigmatic categories.

To syntactic syntagmatics belong structural-syntactic grammatical categories, i.e. types of syntactic relations: subordination (syntax), composition (syntax), predication, attribute, actant (see sentence member).

Syntactic paradigmatics include:

- grammatical categories of the sentence (communicative, or phrase grammatical categories), i.e., the distinguishing features of sentences (statement intent, affirmation/denial (grammar), modality, etc.);
- grammatical categories of syntagms (constituents, sentence members, word combinations), such as grammatical categories of the noun group (definiteness/indefiniteness, gender, number, person), grammatical categories of the predicate (diathesis), grammatical categories of the attribute (degrees of comparison and intensity), etc.

Grammatical categories, according to the part of speech with which they are predominantly expressed, are divided into nominal (characteristic of the noun, adjective, pronoun) and verbal (expressed in verbs). There is no clear boundary

between these types of categories (for example, there are languages where tense is expressed in the name, etc.).

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